

Molecular Complexes of Dichloro-*p*-Benzoquinone Derivatives with Aromatic Amines

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Molecular complexes of substituted anilines with chloranilic acid (I) and dichlorodicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (II) are prepared and investigated by infrared spectroscopy. Anilines substituted at the aromatic ring form two types of compounds involving either a $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction or a proton transfer besides the $\pi-\pi^*$ C.T. with I while II formed the anilide. N-Substituted anilines form compounds involving $\pi-\pi^*$ C.T. or $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ interactions depending on the electronic character of the substituent on the N-atom.

MOLECULAR complexes (M.C.) of the donor-acceptor type can be readily formed between aromatic amines and halogen derivatives of *p*-benzoquinone. The previous studies were mainly confined to the tetrahalogen derivatives chloranil¹, bromanil² and iodoanil³. The investigation of these molecular compounds was carried out using uv-and ir-absorption spectroscopy. The former method was utilised for the determination of the ionisation potentials of several donor molecules⁴.

The present article includes the results of an infrared spectroscopic investigation of the molecular complexes prepared by the interction of 2,5-dichloro-3,6-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (chloranilic acid) (I) or 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (II) with aromatic amines.

The N-substituted anilines are : a) N-methyl aniline, b) N-ethyl aniline, c) N-dimethyl aniline, d) diphenylamine, e) N-acetyl aniline, f) N-methyl anthranilic acid, g) N-dimethyl-*p*-aminobenzaldehyde, h) N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the present investigation were pure laboratory grade chemicals from (BDH).

The molecular complexes were prepared by mixing a hot saturated solution of the donor (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol with an identical one of the acceptor. The solid M. C. separated on mixing or on standing. In the former case, the compounds were purified by boiling with ethanol to ensure freeing from unreacted products. In the latter case, the M.C. were purified by crystallisation. The yield amounts to 90-95% for insoluble compounds and 70-80% for the soluble ones.

Elemental analysis for a series of molecular compounds revealed the formation of 1:1 (donor : acceptor) complexes.

The ir-spectra were recorded, in the solid state applying the KBr disc method, on a Unicam SP 1000 infrared spectrophotometer. Some spectra were obtained by the aid of the Beckman IR-4 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

On allowing the acceptors used in the present investigation to react with aromatic amines (aniline or its phenyl substituted derivatives), only chloranilic acid formed molecular compounds. Chloranil and dichlorodicyano benzoquinone formed anilide derivatives, the ir-spectra of these compounds showed an intense band at 3200-3250 cm^{-1} corresponding to the stretching mode of a secondary amino group⁵. The formation of anilides in case of II can be ascribed to the existence of four acceptor substituents on the quinone nucleus which increases the reactivity of the chlorine atoms. On the other hand, the presence of the OH-groups in I can deactivate the chlorine atoms through their donor character. Accordingly, the molecular complexes of aniline and its phenyl substituted derivatives are confined to chloranilic acid only. To avoid the anilide formation with dichlorodicyano benzoquinone recourse was taken to investigate the molecular compounds with N-substituted anilines.

(A) Molecular Compounds of Anilines with Chloranilic acid :

The reaction of chloranilic acid with anilines leads to the formation of two types of compounds depending on the basicity of the aniline derivative used. This is gathered from the difference in the changes of the spectra of the two types (Fig. 1).

i-Compounds Involving $\pi-\pi^*$ bonding :

This type of molecular compounds takes place with low basicity anilines ($\text{p}K_a \geq 3.0$). The spectra of this class can be considered as an overlap of the spectra of the components with some shifts in the bands. The two ν_{OH} bands of chloranilic acid at 3235 and 3120 cm^{-1} are generally shifted to lower wavenumbers which is also the case for the two carbonyl bands at 1670 and 1637 cm^{-1} . This shift indicates a stronger intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the molecular complex in comparison to the free chloranilic acid molecule.

Fig. I. ir-spectra of chloranilic acid and its molecular complexes with phenyl substituted anilines.

- a) chloranilic acid. b) *o*-NO₂-aniline complex.
c) 2,4-di-Cl-aniline complex.

Fig. II. ir-spectra of dichloro-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone and its molecular complexes with N-substituted anilines.

- a) dichloro-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone
b) N-acetyl aniline complex.
c) N, N, N', N'-tetramethyl *p*-phenylenediamine complex.

The stronger hydrogen bonding in the molecular complex is substantiated by the shift of the δ_{OH} bands at 1290 and 1270 cm^{-1} to higher wavenumbers⁶ and those of the ν_{C-OH} at 1212 and 1170 cm^{-1} to lower values.

The strengthening of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the molecular complex results from the intermolecular charge transfer from the aniline molecule as donor to chloranilic acid as acceptor. This involves the location of a π -electron from the highest filled orbital on the anilino ring to the lowest vacant level on the ring of chloranilic acid i.e. $\pi-\pi^*$ type.

The occurrence of the intermolecular charge transfer is gathered from the shift of the ν_{CH} bands of the donor molecules to higher wavenumbers⁷⁻⁹. The ν_{NH_2} bands display also a slight shift to higher wavenumbers indicating a decrease of the electron density on the aniline ring.

ii-Molecular compounds comprising proton transfer and $\pi-\pi^$ bonding :*

These molecular compounds display large changes in their spectra compared to those of their components. The ν_{OH} band of chloranilic acid at 3235 cm^{-1} and the ν_{NH_2} bands of the anilines within the 3300-3500 cm^{-1} range are no more observed in the spectra of these molecular compounds. Instead of these bands, a series of broad intense bands appear within the 3000-2400 cm^{-1} with broad peaks at 2920-2840, 2740-2680 and 2640-2580 cm^{-1} . These bands correspond to the stretching mode of the N-H groups in the anilinium ion¹⁰, hence the second type of molecular compounds would involve the transfer of a proton from one OH-group of chloranilic acid to the NH₂-group of the aniline derivative. The disappearance of the ν_{OH} bands at 3235 cm^{-1} is accompanied by the vanishing of the two bands at 1290 and 1212 cm^{-1} due to the δ_{OH} and ν_{C-OH} modes.

The C=O bands shift to lower wavenumbers with the higher frequency band displays a large shift such that it interacts strongly with the other C=O band. In some cases the low frequency C=O band appears as a shoulder or intermingles with the other C=O band forming a single broad band. The apparent lowering of the C=O band can be explained by the strong polarising influence of the neighbouring phenate ion.

The OH-bands at 3120 and 1170 cm^{-1} are shifted to lower wavenumbers while that at 1270 cm^{-1} display the opposite behaviour. This is analogous to the shifts observed with the first class of molecular compounds and can be explained in the same manner i.e. increased strength of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding involving the remaining OH-group as a result of the intermolecular $\pi-\pi^*$ C. T. interaction. The existence of the $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction is supported by the shift of the ν_{CH} bands of the donor molecules to higher wavenumbers. Thus the bonding in this class involves the $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction and an electrostatic attraction between the positive and negative charges on the ions forming the molecular complex. Based on the above,

the two types of molecular compounds can be formulated as follows :

This shift indicates a certain differentiation in the energies of the two $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups; one $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group

(B) Molecular Compounds of N-Substituted anilines :

Chloranilic acid reacts with the N-substituted anilines under investigation, except N-ethyl aniline, forming molecular complexes involving intermolecular charge transfer. N-ethyl aniline on the other hand forms molecular complex of the charge and proton transfer type. This is gathered from a comparison of the spectral shifts in case of N-substituted anilines with those of phenyl substituted anilines.

The most striking effect is the shift of the higher frequency $\text{C}=\text{O}$ band to higher wavenumbers in the spectra of molecular complexes of a, c and g. This shift recalls the behaviour of C. T. complexes of aromatic nitrocompounds with aniline derivatives involving an $n-\pi^*$ transition⁷⁻⁹. Thus the shift of the carbonyl band to higher wavenumbers can be ascribed to the occurrence of an $n-\pi^*$ interaction. This involves the location of an n-electron from the amino nitrogen to the lowest vacant π -level on the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group. This premise is substantiated by the shift of both $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bands to higher values in case of tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine where the two carbonyl groups of chloranilic acid face two dimethyl amino groups. The $n-\pi^*$ interaction is not possible in case of d and e due to the presence of an acceptor group attached to the nitrogen atom. For f the participation of the lone pair of the nitrogen atom in an intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the carbonyl group.

Molecular complexes of N-substituted anilines with dichloro-dicyanobezoquinone would be of one type only due to the absence of an acidic centre on the acceptor molecule. The $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bands at $1695\text{-}1678\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the free acceptor are shifted to lower wavenumbers due to the intermolecular C.T. interaction between the two rings of the molecules forming the complex. The $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction reflects itself in the shift of the ν_{CH} bands of the donor molecules to higher wavenumbers.

The $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ band shifts to lower values in case of e and f i.e. molecules incapable of participating in the $n-\pi^*$ transition. For a, b, c, g and h the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ band appears into two bands in the spectra of the molecular complexes, these are situated at lower and higher wavenumber compared to the band of the free acceptor.

would suffer an increased polarisation under the influence of the $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction, hence being displayed to lower energies. The other $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group being shifted to higher wavenumbers would be involved in $n-\pi^*$ interaction with the amino nitrogen of the donor molecule. Thus the substituted amino group would face the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group. Based on these information, compounds involving $n-\pi^*$ interaction can be formulated as follows :

On comparing the behaviour of N-substituted anilines with that of phenyl substituted anilines, it can be pointed out that they are not capable of contributing in $n-\pi^*$ bonding with chloranilic acid. This is due to the high n-ionisation potentials of anilines with acceptor substituents. Anilines with donor substituents which facilitate the $n-\pi^*$ transition form molecular compounds in which the lone pair on the nitrogen atom is blocked by proton transfer from the acceptor molecule.

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